

Research Article

Early Detection of Carbon Monoxide in a Car with Car Gas Detector (CARGAS)

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Abstract: Carbon monoxide is an odourless, colourless, and extremely dangerous gas because it can cause poisoning and death if inhaled in high amounts without realizing it. Thus, the Car Gas Detector Project (CARGAS) was developed as an intelligent safety system specifically designed to detect carbon monoxide (CO) gas in vehicles. This system uses MQ-9 sensors to detect CO levels in the vehicle and provide early warning to drivers and passengers to help avoid more serious risks. Alerts will be delivered via buzzers and real-time notifications in the Telegram app, enabling users to act immediately. In addition, the system is equipped with the NEO-6M GPS module, which accurately tracks the vehicle's location in an emergency, and the ESP32-CAM, which enables the transmission of images from the vehicle to relevant parties, such as family members or authorities. All of these components are connected via ESP8266 or ESP32, ensuring efficient data transmission over an internet connection. The test results show that the system works well in providing early warnings and helping users take appropriate safety measures. The testing phase has shown CARGAS can provide visual monitoring and real-time detection quickly at a rate of 0.05 m/s. The CARGAS project has successfully fulfilled all three main objectives: building a gas leak detection system using MQ-9 sensors, developing a real-time alert notification function via Telegram with an ESP8266 module, and designing a location detection system using the NEO-6M GPS module to inform the vehicle's position during emergencies.

Keywords: CARGAS; car; CO; detector; death; early.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon monoxide (CO) is a colourless and odourless gas that is extremely poisonous. CO could harm humans because the body absorbs it in minutes, binds to haemoglobin, and thereby prevents the blood from transporting oxygen, causing tissues to become oxygen-deprived (B. Miles, S. Chikhi, & E. B. Bourennane, 2019). A tragic incident in Malaysia on September 19, 2020, highlighted this risk when four friends resting inside a Honda Odyssey with the engine running were exposed to lethal CO levels, resulting in three deaths. This study also examines the limitations of traditional CO detection systems, which typically rely solely on local alarms without remote notifications, reducing their effectiveness in emergencies.

Figure 1. Deaths from accidental carbon monoxide poisoning from 1999 to 2022 (<https://www.usafacts.org>)

Gas leaks in vehicles, especially those that use Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) or Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG), can be life-threatening as they are difficult to detect manually. Existing gas detector devices only issue alarms without mobile notifications, and most lack location detection. The Car Gas Detector (CARGAS) project addressed the shortfall by developing a system that automatically sends real-time alerts and vehicle locations via Telegram, improving security and speeding up emergency response times.

This study aims to develop an in-vehicle gas detection system to enhance passenger safety through three key implementations: First, constructing a gas leakage detector capable of identifying hazardous gas concentrations that may escape manual detection. Second, integrating real-time warning notifications to mobile devices enables immediate user response when dangerous gas levels are detected. Third, incorporating GPS-based vehicle location tracking that automatically shares position data via messaging platforms like Telegram, particularly crucial when drivers become incapacitated, to facilitate rapid emergency response and victim localization.

CARGAS aims to develop a gas leak detection system for sedan vehicles to improve safety. The integration of advanced detection and control systems can significantly mitigate the risks associated with CNG gas leaks. or usage in industrial processes, home uses, and transportation, compressed natural gas, or CNG, has shown great promise as an alternative fuel (Elangkumaravelan, K & Mani, Prasannakumar, 2024). The system includes gas detectors, real-time alert notifications via mobile devices, and automatic location features using apps like Telegram. The focus of the project is on vehicles used by the public and any company that provides vehicles to staff, as they are at risk of gas leaks and require additional safety measures. Other than that, this project focuses on aiming to enhance vehicle safety by developing an innovative gas-leakage detection system.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

CARGAS utilizes the MQ-9 sensor, which detects CO levels inside the vehicle and provides early warnings to drivers and passengers to prevent serious risks. The data collected by this sensor is used to trigger a buzzer alarm and to send real-time notifications via the Telegram application, enabling

users to take immediate action. Additionally, the system is equipped with a NEO-6M GPS module, which accurately tracks the vehicle’s location in an emergency, and an ESP32-CAM, which allows transmission of images from inside the vehicle to designated recipients, such as family members or authorities.

The other hardware modules used to develop CARGAS as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. CARGAS Hardware Module Function

No	Name	Description
1	MQ-9 Gas Sensor Module	To detect the presence of carbon monoxide gas
2	Electronic Piezo Buzzer 3V	To produce a sound or an alarm
3	ESP32-CAM	As the camera supported Wi-Fi and Bluetooth connections
4	ESP8266	To send a real-time notification
5	GPS NEO-6M	To track the vehicle’s location

Figure 2 shows the CARGAS in a preliminary sketch in a circuit that connects all the hardware modules, and Figure 3 shows the CARGAS’s components placed in the casing.

Figure 2. CARGAS in a preliminary sketch

Figure 3. CARGAS in the casing

Figure 4 shows a notification sent directly in the Telegram application when the sensor detects CO at a dangerous level. The notifications included that the location was tracked and an image was captured.

Figure 4. Real-time notifications

Thus, CARGAS is a project developed as an in-vehicle gas detection system to enhance passenger safety. It integrates sensor technology, a buzzer for alerts, and an alert notification system

that includes location and images. CARGAS was tested and proved to function as intended, as set in the initial stages.

3. FINDINGS

The Car Gas Detector (CARGAS) is an intelligent safety system specifically designed to detect carbon monoxide (CO) gas in vehicles. Following its development, a series of product testing procedures was conducted to evaluate its functionality and performance. Upon completion of these tests, researchers administered a survey to further assess user perceptions of CARGAS's operational effectiveness. The survey feedback provides valuable insights for continuous improvement, enabling future enhancements to optimize the system's performance, reliability, and overall efficiency.

Table 2. Survey results

No	Item	Agree (%)
1	Considering installing CARGAS	60
2	Real-time notification is important	37
3	CARGAS can improve vehicle safety	70
4	Sending photos to family is a useful feature	67
5	Recommend CARGAS to family and friends	73

Table 2 presents the overall results obtained from the respondents based on five survey questions. Four out of the five items received positive responses exceeding 60%, reflecting a high level of user satisfaction. The findings indicate that respondents believe CARGAS enhances vehicle safety through the integration of real-time notification alerts and the ability to send photos to family members. Furthermore, most respondents expressed their willingness to install the system in their vehicles and to recommend CARGAS to their family and friends. In conclusion, the results suggest that the CARGAS system demonstrates reliable functionality and operates effectively in fulfilling its intended purpose.

4. DISCUSSION

This CARGAS consists of several key components, including a gas sensor, a buzzer, a camera, an ESP32-CAM and a GPS tracker. It is designed to efficiently detect carbon monoxide in the vehicle. Upon detection, the system automatically notifies family members or relevant authorities through buzzer alarm, message and image notification. As it is still in early stages, CARGAS is placed in a display box as shown in Figure 5. As this project has considerable potential for further enhancing and expanding this project. Future developments could focus on improving sensor sensitivity to detect not only carbon monoxide but also a wider range of hazardous gases. Additionally, incorporating a feature that can identify the specific location of a gas leak within the vehicle would significantly aid in both repair and preventive maintenance efforts, thereby improving overall system effectiveness and safety assurance.

Figure 5. CARGAS

5. CONCLUSION

The Car Gas Detector (CARGAS) is an intelligent safety system specifically designed to detect carbon monoxide (CO) gas in vehicles. Following its development, a series of product testing procedures was conducted to evaluate its functionality and performance. Upon completion of these tests, researchers administered a survey to further assess user perceptions of CARGAS's operational effectiveness. The survey feedback provides valuable insights for continuous improvement, enabling future enhancements to optimize the system's performance, reliability, and overall efficiency.

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